

Pomak: An idiosyncratic East South Slavic language?

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Abstract

This paper is a brief attempt to highlight some innovative and conservative traits that set apart the Pomak dialect continuum from its close relatives (Bulgarian and Macedonian) within East South Slavic. At times such traits even bring Pomak closer to North Slavic languages, i.e. ones that do not belong to the East South Slavic group. Other traits are unique to Pomak in terms not only of Slavic languages but of Indo-European languages in general. The conclusion is that, in terms of a synchronic and typological approach, the Pomak dialect continuum should rather be viewed as a separate, non-standardised East South Slavic language rather than as a dialect of any other Slavic language.

Keywords: *Bulgarian, East South Slavic, Macedonian, Pomak, Slavic, non-standardised languages*

1. Introduction: History and scripts of Pomak

Pomak (endonym: *Pomácko*, *Pomáhcku* or other variants, depending on dialect) is a non-standardised East South Slavic (ESS) language variety mainly spoken in the region of Greek Thrace, as well as in places of Pomak diaspora, given that Pomak workers may be found all over Europe (Constantinides 2007: 35). As all ESS languages, Pomak largely derives from a Slavic language once spoken from Central Europe to the Balkans, which came to be known as Old Church Slavonic (Kyranoudis 1995: 165) in its version that was standardised by the Saints Cyril and Methodius in Moravia for liturgical purposes after 862 AD (Encyclopaedia Britannica 1969: 959); here we will call it Old Church Slavonic (OCS). Bulgarians and Macedonians (who do not recognise a Pomak language) each claim OCS as the direct ancestor of exclusively Bulgarian or Macedonian (Kamusella 2008: 34), although Pomak can be shown to retain OCS traits lost in the other ESS languages. Pomak can be shown to have followed its own evolutionary course. Moreover, in comparison to all ESS languages, Pomak exhibits a more profound phonological, morphological, morphosyntactic and lexical influence by Medieval and Modern Greek (Krimpas 2020: 196) and, due to the predominantly Muslim religion of its speakers, a more profound lexical and phonotactical influence by Ottoman and Modern Turkish (Constantinides 2008: 286). A synchronic typological approach can trace conservative and innovative traits of Pomak in comparison with its standardised close relatives (Bulgarian and Macedonian).

The basic source of Pomak vocabulary is Old Church Slavonic. Numerous OCS words only survive in Pomak, while they have been lost in standardised ESS languages. Some OCS words have retained their basic meaning in Pomak, while others have changed it. Interestingly, Pomak has retained some OCS words that do not exist in standardised ESS languages. Some examples are the following:

Pomak	Old Church Slavonic
nagá 'foot'	< нога 'id.', cf. Bulgarian <i>крак</i>
mrázi 'it is cold'	< мразити 'id.', cf. Bulgarian <i>студено е</i>
prásno 'milk'	< прѣсьнь 'sweet', cf. Bulgarian <i>пресен</i> 'fresh'

A random lexical comparison among Slavic languages suggests that Pomak has its own characteristic vocabulary.

Pomak	Bulgarian	Macedonian	Serbian/ Croatian	Czech	Polish	Russian
adbávem ‘to spend; to spoil’	харча, развалям	издавам, оплъачкувам	pokvariti	strávit zkazit	spędzić zepsuć	проводить портиться
bíjem (< OCS biti ‘to beat’), cf. MGk. κρούω ‘to beat; to stink’	воня, смърдя	смрдам	smrdjeti	smrdět, zápáchat, páchnout	śmierdzieć	вонять
cótka ‘pimple; rash’	пъпка,	пришт, брзање	bubuljica, navala	purínek spěch	pryszcz pośpiech	прыщ спешка
fírem ‘to hunt’	ловувам	ловам	loviti	lov	polowanie	охота
fsúnavom ‘to approach’	приближавам	приодам	pristup	přístup	zbliżać się	подход
hálom ‘to touch’	докосвам	допирам	dodirati	dotek	dotykać	трогать
koftáč ‘beak’	клюн	клун	kljun	zobák	dziób	клюв
krílem ‘to fly’ letí	летя	летам	letjeti	letět	latać	летать, лететь
krop ‘short (of stature)’	къс, нисък	низок	nizak	nížký	niski	низкий
lűbem ‘to kiss’	целувам	бакнувам	ljubiti	políbit	po całować	целовать
méhnom ‘to annoy; to harass’	мязам	изнервирам	dosadivati, uznemiravati	otravovat obtěžovat	drażnić, nękać	раздражать, беспокоить
mótrah ‘rag’	парцал	партал	krpa	hadr	szmatka	тряпка
padsúnavom ‘to slip’	подхлъзвам	слизувам	skliziti se	uklouznout	poślizgać się	скользить
pítem ‘to flatten’	сплесквам	израмнувам	poravnati	vyrovnat	spłaszczyć	сгладить
prýnkom ‘to throw’	хвърлям	фрлам	baciti	házet	rzucić	бросать
pýhom ‘to kick’	ритам	клоцам	udariti (nogom), ritati (for horses)	kopnout	kopnąć	пинать
sáero ‘colostrum’	коластра	коластрум	kolastrum	kolostrum	siara	молозиво
súnom ‘to move; to remove’	движа, премахвам	поместам, отстранам	pomeriti, ukloniti	pohybovat odebrat	przenosić, usuwać	двигаться удалять
svórtom ‘to lower (volume)’	намалявам	намалувам	smanjiti	snížít	obniżać	уменьшить

tačilo 'custom'	обычай	обичај	običaj	zvyk	zwyczaj	обычай
úparka '(a) burn'	изгаряне	изгореница	opekotina	spálenina	oparzenie	ожог
valésavom 'to pay attention'	внимавам	внимавам	paziti	dávat pozor	zwróc uwagę	обращать внимание
vézen 'pink'	розов	розов	ružičast	růžový	różowy	розовый
zábelo 'kavurma; meat preserved in fat'	каварма	печење	pečenje	praženi	prażenie	жарка
zabláevom 'to delay'	забавям	одложувам	odgoditi	zdržovat	opóźniać	отложить

Pomak has been written in a variety of alphabets and scripts. The Perso-Arabic script was sometimes used to write Pomak, given the predominantly Muslim religion of its speakers. Later a Greek-based script was devised by Petros D. Theocharidis. One of the authors of this paper, Ritvan Karahođa, a native speaker of Pomak, has devised several Greek, Latin and Cyrillic-based alphabets to write Pomak. In the framework of the PHILOTIS project (<http://philotis.athenarc.gr/> and <https://www.ilsp.gr/projects/filotis-el/>), two of the authors of this paper, namely Ritvan Karahođa and Panagiotis G. Krimpas, devised a brand new Pomak Latin-based alphabet consisting of 33 letters (graphs), which is used throughout this paper as well as in all deliverables of the PHILOTIS project. Its authors aspire for this alphabet to be widely accepted and established among Pomak-speakers. In comparison with older alphabets, which used digraphs, two compulsory accent marks etc., its main advantages are the following: a) it uses one graph for one sound of (depending on dialect) phoneme, i.e. it exhibits 1:1 correspondence between graphs and sounds or phonemes; b) it is based on existing Latin-based alphabets currently used to write Slavic and Baltic languages; c) it uses just four diacritics and two special characters borrowed from Scandinavian languages; d) it does not reflect the devoicing of final voiced consonants, which allows for a consistent orthography of both the stem and the inflected forms; e) it better reflects pronunciation; and f) it can be used with or without accents (here it is used with accents for the reader's ease; the accent is always the acute). This new Pomak alphabet comprises the following letters (graphs; in brackets we give the phonetic value of graphs with diacritis and special characters): Aa, Ææ [ɛɛ], Bb, Cc [t͡s], Čč [t͡ʃ], Dd, Ee, Ff, Gg, Ğğ [d͡z], Ğğ [d͡ʒ], Hh, Ii, Jj, Kk, Ll, Ľl [ʎ], Mm, Nn, Ńń [ɲ], Oo, Øø [ø], Pp, Rr, Ss, Šš [ʃ], Tt, Uu, Üü [y], Vv, Yy [i], Zz, Žž [ʒ].

2. Conservative and innovative peculiarities in Pomak

Apart from its distinctive vocabulary, Pomak differs from its close relatives (Bulgarian and Macedonian) in many traits; here we present six innovative and four conservative phonological, morphological and morphosyntactic ones, some of which bring Pomak closer to North (traditionally: East and West) than East South Slavic languages. However, do note that the innovative vs. conservative distinction is conventional, as some traits that are labelled 'conservative' may at the same time be innovative in other aspects.

Innovative traits

1. Two close front rounded vowels (/ø/ and /y/) with phonemic value
2. Change of unstressed /o/ into /a/ and stressed /e/ into /o/ in various environments
3. Numerous Greek and Turkish loanwords
4. Functional merger of genitive and dative into morphological dative
5. A tripartite definite article in the framework of a tripartite deixis
6. A *WHERE*-relativiser

Conservative traits

7. Reflection of yat (ѣ/ě) as an /εe/ diphthong
8. Masculine personal form in the adjectival declension (adjectives, participles and 3rd person plural pronouns)
9. Noun inflection (cases, although the Pomak system is very reduced in comparison to the Old Church Slavonic one)
10. Residual infinitive (but without the *-ti* ending)

2.1 Two close front rounded vowels (/ø/ and /y/) with phonemic value

The close-mid front rounded vowel /ø/ derives either from OCS little yus (ѣ) /ě/ or from OCS strong front yer (ѣ) (Kyranoudis 1996: 168; Lunt 1966: 19), while the close front rounded vowel /y/ usually derives from Slavonic ~~ѣ~~ /jǫ/ and ю /ju/ (Kyranoudis 1996: 170; Lunt 1966: 25). Those phonemes is only documented in Polabian, where they have evolved from other vowels (Polański 2002: 799–806). Some examples from Pomak are the following:

Pomak	Old Church Slavonic
glødam ‘to look’	< глѣдати ‘id.’
løk ‘light, <i>adj.</i> ’	< льгѣкъ ‘id.’
lűbem ‘to kiss’	< любити ‘love’
lüt ‘sour’	< лють ‘difficult’

The existence of those phonemes typologically connects Pomak with more northern Slavic languages.

2.2 Change of unstressed /o/ (occasionally also unstressed /e/) into /a/ and stressed /e/ into /o/ in various positions

Like Russian and Belarusian and unlike its ESS close relatives (Bulgarian and Macedonian), Pomak changes unstressed /o/ into /a/ (in some variants further reduced to /e/) in various positions. Occasionally, like Belarusian and unlike Bulgarian and Macedonian, it changes also unstressed /e/ into /a/. Besides, like Polish, Sorbian, Kashubian, Polabian, Russian, Belarusian and Ukrainian, and unlike Bulgarian and Macedonian, Pomak changes stressed /e/ into /o/ in various positions:

Pomak	Old Church Slavonic
nagá ‘foot’	< нога ‘id.’ (cf. Russian нога [nɐˈga] ‘id.’)

žaná ‘woman’	< жена ‘id.’ (cf. Belarusian жанчына ‘id.’)
žóny ‘women’	< жены ‘id.’ (cf. Polish żony ‘wives’)

The existence of those vowel changes typologically connects Pomak with more northern Slavic languages.

2.3. Numerous Greek and Turkish loanwords

Many religious and technical terms are expressed by means of loanwords from Medieval/Modern Greek and Turkish.

2.3.1. Examples from Greek

Pomak contains considerably more numerous Medieval and Modern Greek loanwords than its close relatives – at least in their standardised variants. Such Greek loanwords have been absorbed during the centuries of co-existence between speakers of Greek and East South Slavic. Modern Greek words come either from neighbouring north Greek dialects or, more recently, from Standard Modern Greek in order to denote numerous abstract concepts and modern life utilities (Kyranoudis 1996: 179-180):

Pomak	Greek
léfter ‘single’	< λεύτερος ‘free’ < Anc.Gk. ελεύθερος
kaléko ‘uncle’	< καλέ, vocative of καλός ‘good’ + -ko (Slavic diminutive suffix)
hárkama ‘metal bucket’	< χάρκωμα (dialectal) ‘copper pot’ < χάλκωμα < Anc.Gk. χαλκός ‘copper’
gurída ‘sour grape’	< αγουρίδα < άγουρος ‘unripe’ < Anc.Gk. άωρος ‘early, premature’
anavolí ‘postponement’	< αναβολή ‘id.’
gimnásje ‘high school’	< γυμνάσιο ‘id.’
lohagózin ‘captain (military)’	< λοχαγός ‘id.’ (although the -oz- part may point to Turkish mediation, i.e. *lohagoz; alternatively, it can reflect the Modern Greek pronunciation of /s/ as /z/ before voiced consonants, e.g. ο λοχαγός μας ‘our captain’ [oloxa'ʒozmas])
ispráktorozin ‘ticket conductor’	< εισπράκτορας ‘id.’ (although the -oz- part may point to Turkish mediation, i.e. *ispraktoroz; alternatively, it can reflect the Modern Greek pronunciation of /s/ as /z/ before voiced consonants, e.g. ο εισπράκτοράς μας ‘our ticket conductor’ [ois'prakto'razmas])

2.3.2. Examples from Turkish

Many Turkish loanwords have been borrowed during the Ottoman era (Kyranoudis 1996: 179-180), but modern Turkish also provides Pomak with numerous terms denoting concepts of everyday and modern life, such as terms of science, technology, administration, many of which are of French or Arabic origin in Turkish (cf. Kyranoudis

1996: 179-180) (however, there are lexical differences among Pomak dialects, especially as far as loanwords are concerned: some dialects bear a stronger Greek influence, other a stronger Turkish one, while in Greece there are also more Northern Pomak dialects that show Bulgarian influence):

Pomak	Turkish
altón ‘gold’	< altın ‘id.’
denís ‘sea’	< deniz ‘id.’
kasabá ‘town’	< kasaba ‘id.’
beš ‘five’	< beş ‘id.’
lastík ‘elastic, tire’	< lastık ‘id.’
mákina ‘engine, machine’	< makine ‘id.’
belidjá ‘community’	< belediye ‘id.’
daktór / doktór ‘medical doctor’	< doktor ‘id.’

The existence of numerous Greek and Turkish loanwords typologically connects Pomak with Balkan languages (both Slavic and non-Slavic).

2.4 Functional merger of genitive and dative into morphological dative

Most Balkan languages such as Albanian, Romanian or Modern Greek exhibit syncretism of genitive and dative cases (Thomason 1999: 316; Krimpas 2007: 52–53) with both forms having been merged into morphological genitive. In other words, dative has been typologically assimilated by genitive. Yet in Pomak the opposite is the case, since genitive has been morphologically assimilated by the dative as clearly shown by the morphological endings, which derive from their Old Church Slavonic dative counterparts, a situation that has a parallel only in Tsakonian, a mostly Doric-based Greek dialect (e.g. *γυναίσι* ‘of the woman; to/for the woman’, *gen./dat. case* < Anc.Gk. *γυναίκι* ‘to/for the woman’, *dative case*) (Krimpas 2017: 183–185). The phenomenon is unique among the Slavic languages, at least in their standardised versions. According to Krimpas (2017: 184–185), the old dual genitive in *-u*, which sounded like the singular dative in *-u*, may have been the starting point for this merger, but the expansion and establishment of the dative form in the function of the genitive may have been further boosted by the similarly sounding genitive singular of second declension nouns in Greek (*-ου /-u/*), which first influenced masculine and neuter Pomak nouns to then spread to feminine nouns as well; now, if one considers that Greek has a distinct form of genitive and accusative and that OCS had an identical genitive and accusative singular in masculine animate nouns, it becomes rather clear why Pomaks – probably Greek-Slavic bilinguals – searched for a different genitive ending and borrowed it from the dative.

	Singular	Plural
Nominative	čuláek ‘man’	čuláekove ‘men’
Genitive/Dative	čuláeku ‘of a man; to/for a man’	čuláekovem ‘men's’

Nominative	barčina ‘mountain’	barčíny ‘mountains’
Genitive/Dative	barčínoj ‘of a mountain; to/for a mountain’	barčínom ‘of mountains; to/for mountains’

Nominative	sélo ‘village’	selá ‘villages’
Genitive/Dative	sélu ‘of a village ; to/for a village’	sélom ‘of villages; to/for villages’

The merger of genitive/dative typologically connects Pomak with non-Slavic Balkan languages, but even more so with Tsakonian Greek.

2.5 A tripartite definite article in the framework of a tripartite deixis

Another Pomak trait is the declinable tripartite suffixed definite article as well as an overall tripartite deixis system. Most Slavic languages, including OCS, lack a definite article. The only Slavic languages with definite articles (always suffixed and derived from demonstrative pronouns) are ESS languages (Bulgarian, Macedonian, Pomak) as well as the Northern dialects of Russian (Sussex & Cubberley 2006: 521–526). Unlike Pomak, Bulgarian has a virtually indeclinable suffixed definite with no definiteness gradation. Macedonian, similarly to Bulgarian, has a virtually indeclinable definite article, which, although tripartite like the one found in Pomak (Krimpas 2020: 185), the definiteness gradation uses one article not found in Pomak, while the other two articles (which do exist in Pomak) are somehow differently distributed in terms of definiteness gradation. The nominative case of the tripartite Pomak definite article is as follows for the three genders (masculine, feminine, neuter) and the two numbers (singular, plural):

Degree of definiteness	Gender	Singular	Plural
1st	masculine	-os	-se
	feminine	-sa	-se
	neutral	-so	-sa
2nd	masculine	-ot	-te
	feminine	-ta	-te
	neutral	-to	-ta
3rd	masculine	-on	-ne
	feminine	-na	-ne
	neutral	-no	-na

The inflection of the article for case is as follows:

Type	Noun	Article	1 st /-s-/	2 nd /-t-/	3 rd /-n-/
Cases					
Masculine čulák = man					
Singular					
Nominative	čulák	-os/-ot/-on	čulákos	čulákot	čulákon
Gen./Dat.	čuláku	-se/-te/-ne	čulákuse	čulákute	čulákune
Accusative	čuláka	-se/-te/-ne	čulákase	čulákate	čulákane
Vocative	čuláku	—	—	—	—
Plural					
Nominative	čulákove	-se/-te/-ne	čulákovese	čulákovete	čulákovene

Gen./Dat.	čulákovem	-se/-te/-ne	čulákovemse	čulákovemte	čulákovemne
Accusative	čulákově	-se/-te/-ne	čulákovese	čulákovete	čulákovene
Vocative	čulákově	—	—	—	—
Feminine <i>barčina</i> = mountain					
Singular					
Nominative	barčina	-sa/-ta/-na	barčínasa	barčínata	barčínana
Gen./Dat.	barčíněj	-se/-te/-ne	barčínějse	barčínějte	barčínějne
Accusative	barčíně	-so/-to/-no	barčíněso	barčíněto	barčíněno
Vocative	barčíně	—	—	—	—
Plural					
Nominative	barčíně	-se/-te/-ne	barčíněse	barčíněte	barčíněne
Gen./Dat.	barčíněm	-se/-te/-ne	barčíněmse	barčíněmte	barčíněmne
Accusative	barčíně	-se/-te/-ne	barčíněse	barčíněte	barčíněne
Vocative	barčíně	—	—	—	—
Neutral <i>sélo</i> = village					
Singular					
Nominative	sélo	-so/-to/-no	sélosó	séloto	sélonó
Gen./Dat.	sélú	-se/-te/-ne	sélúse	sélúte	sélúne
Accusative	sélo	-so/-to/-no	sélosó	séloto	sélonó
Vocative	sélo	—	—	—	—
Plural					
Nominative	selá	-sa/-ta/-na	selása	seláta	selána
Gen./Dat.	sélóm	-se/-te/-ne	sélómse	sélómte	sélómne
Accusative	selá	-sa/-ta/-na	selása	seláta	selána
Vocative	selá	—	—	—	—

The three forms of Pomak article denote three degrees of proximity of the speaker or the listener to the object in question (Kokkas 2004: 46, 72, 88). The first definiteness degree denotes something/someone close to the speaker, e.g. *žanása* ‘the woman here next to me, this woman’. The second definiteness degree denotes something/someone close to the listener, e.g. *žanáta* ‘the woman next to you, that woman’. And the third definiteness degree denotes something/someone remote from both the speaker and the listener, which is why it is also used to denote something/someone out of sight and/or perceived in an abstract manner (Kyranoudis 1996-1998: 172), e.g. *žanána* ‘the woman (in general), the woman somewhere out of sight’.

It is worth saying a few words about the origin of this tripartite article. In particular, it seems that as early as the 13th century the OCS demonstrative pronouns, which could be pre- or post-posed, became suffixed to later acquire the function of definite article (Adamou 2009: 6). It is certain that suffixed definite articles, whether tripartite or not, are innovations, but they did not develop at the same time within all ESS languages (Adamou 2009: 6-7). What is for sure is that the tripartite article in Pomak is an exact reflection of the OCS tripartite demonstrative pronouns: *сѣ - сѹ - се / тѣ - та - то / онѣ - она - оно* in a post-posed position (Kanevska-Nikolova 2006: 21, 207; Lunt 1966: 52), as well as that Greek has been the catalyst for the development of articles in EES languages, not exclusively via the Bible translations from Greek into OCS as often claimed (Dimitrova-Vulchanova & Vulchanov 2011: 160–178), but rather due to a prolonged *in situ* Greek-Slavic bilingualism among East South Slavs (including Pomaks), i.e. through direct language contact (Krimpas 2020: 185–186). This constitutes a marked difference from

the other ESS language with tripartite definite article, Macedonian. The latter exhibits a different reflection of the tripartite definite article, which *inter alia* suggests that it developed it independently from Pomak and, therefore, is a different language. As illustrated in the two next tables (Constantinides 2021: 58-59), Macedonian has a V-article instead of the Pomak S-article:

Pomak				Macedonian		
Gender	Type	Singular	Plural	Type	Singular	Plural
masculine	1st	-os	-se	1st	-OB	-ve
feminine		-sa	-se		-Ba	-ve
neutral		-so	-sa		-BO	-Ba
masculine	2nd	-ot	-te	2nd	-OT	-te
feminine		-ta	-te		-Ta	-te
neutral		-to	-ta		-TO	-Ta
masculine	3rd	-on	-ne	3rd	-OH	-ne
feminine		-na	-ne		-Ha	-ne
neutral		-no	-na		-HO	-Ha

Pomak				Macedonian		
Proximity	Type	Singular	Plural	Type	Singular	Plural
the mother here	1st	žanása	žónyse	1st	женава	жениве
the mother there	2nd	žanáta	žónyte	2st	жената	жените
the mother far away	3rd	žanána	žónyne	3rd	женана	женине

According to Krimpas (2020: 186–187), the choice of the S-demonstrative pronoun as the close-to-the-speaker definite article (giving *-os* when added to masculine nouns) may have been encouraged by the presence of the omnipresent Greek masculine nominative singular in */-os/* to then spread to the other genders as well. The same could be true also of the Medieval Greek masculine accusative singular in */-on/*, which may have influenced the development of the N-demonstrative pronoun into the remote-from-both N-definite article. If this is correct, the Greek-Slavic bilingualism of Pomaks must have been very early.

Interestingly, an exclusively Pomak innovation not found in any other Slavic (or even in other Indo-European) language, is that the tripartite contrast in question is not limited to the definite article, but it extends to the whole deixis system, this is why it is found both in inflected parts of speech such as demonstrative pronouns, and in uninflected ones such as adverbs of time, place, quantity, manner etc. In all cases the *-s(-)*, *-t(-)*, *-n(-)* distinction provides the basis for such a contrast (Papadimitriou 2008: 209; Constantinides 2021: 61). The tripartite system in demonstrative pronouns is illustrated below:

Deixis	Determinative Deictics			Qualitive Deictics		
	masculine	feminine	neutral	masculine	feminine	neutral
S- proximity to the speaker	isazí 'this one'	isázi 'this one'	isazí 'this one'	isakvózen 'such one here'	isakvázne 'such one here'	isakvózne 'such one here'
T-proximity to the listener	itazí 'this'	itázi 'this'	itazí 'this'	itakvózen 'such one'	itakvázne 'such one'	itakvózne 'such one'
N-distance from both	inazí 'that'	inázi 'that'	inazí 'that'	inakvózen 'such one there'	inakvázne 'such one there'	inakvózne 'such one there'

As far as the uninflected parts of speech are concerned, an intense division of space and time is revealed by such a tripartite distinction (Constantinides 2007: 75; Papadimitriou 2013: 369; Adamou 2009: 3; Constantinides 2021: 61). The following examples illustrate this contrast:

Deixis	S-form identification with the speaker/here/now	T-form identification with the interlocutor/there/in the past	N-form identification with someone else/in the future/repeatedly
Basal lexemes			
Suffixed			
kugá 'when?'	kugása 'when/whenever (regarding me/in the present)'	kugáta when / whenever (regarding you / in the past)	kugána when / whenever 'regarding him/her/it in the future'
kólko 'how much?'	kólkoso 'so much (for me)'	kólkoto 'so much (for you)'	kólkono 'so much (for him/her/it)'
kak 'how?'	káksa as I	kákta as you	kákna 'as he/she/it'
kadé 'where?'	kadésa 'where I'	kadéta 'where you'	kadéna 'where he/she/it there'
Prefixed			
(kólko) 'how much?'	isélkus 'so much here/so much for me'	itélkus 'so much there/so much for you'	inélkus 'so much over there/so much for him/her/it'
-ýj here / there	isýj near here	ityj there by you	inyj far there
Notes: 1. A Pomak word in brackets [] means that it is very rare (Spoken Testimony P.M., E-63-02, Nicolaos Th. Constantinides' Archive of Oral History). 2. A Pomak word in parentheses () means it is likely to be the original form for the corresponding derivative.			

Let us note that the phenomenon of tripartite contrast concerning time also occurs in an early stage of OCS as well, but the pronoun stem is prefixed to the temporal morpheme -zda (< zодъ 'year, time'): *когда* 'when', *тогда* 'then', *оногда* 'now' (Lunt 1966: 67). The above discussion clearly suggests that Pomak has a complex system of tripartite relationships, initially expressed through the tripartite definite article to then spread to multiple determiner levels. This system is spontaneously applied in Pomak and may take

idiolectal forms as well (Constantinides 2021: 61-62). Moreover, the tripartite distinction in Pomak shows a special connection with the 1st, 2nd, or 3rd person (singular or plural):

No	Kind	Person	Pronoun
1.	Identity	1st singular	“ja” or “I”
2.	Collective Identity	1st plural	“nýje” or “we”
3.	Otherness	2nd & 3rd singular	“ty” or “you” “toj-tja-to” or “he-she-it”
4.	Multitude of Otherness	2nd & 3rd plural	“výje” or “you” “tíje (masc.pers.)-to (masc.non-pers.)-to-to” or “they”

The above system reveals a tripartite distinction between identity and otherness, while a tripartite system of determiners and contrasts also occurs, which adds extra categorisations to the ‘identity-vs.-otherness’ system itself. In order to understand the further relationships of identity-vs.-otherness within the system of the tripartite-determiner contrast one has to consider several components of human identity and otherness, in more general terms: a) Identity appears as ‘the first singular person’, which consists of the personal pronoun *ja* ‘I, me’, both in Pomak and English; b) collective identity occurs as ‘the first plural person’, which is expressed by means of the personal pronoun *nýje* ‘we’; c) otherness comes out as ‘the second singular person’, which is expressed by the pronoun *ty* ‘you’, while it also shows up as ‘the third singular person’, which comprises three genders expressed via the personal pronouns *toj-tja-to* ‘he-she-it’; d) the multitude of otherness exists as ‘the second plural person’, which is presented by the personal pronoun *výje* ‘you’, while it also appears as ‘the third plural person’, which comprises three genders expressed via the personal pronouns *tíje-to-to-to* ‘they’.

However, Pomak does not stop at what is usual for Slavic (and other Indo-European) languages, but evidences further levels of identity and otherness; it structures them in space and time, since the main principle of the three person distinction acquires additional categorisations in the identity-vs.-otherness system, as illustrated below:

	1st person			2nd person			3rd person		
1.	ja	concerning me	-s	ty	concerning me	-t	toj-tja-to	concerning me	-n
2.	ja	concerning you	-t	ty	concerning you	-s	toj-tja-to	concerning you	-t
3.	ja	concerning him-her-it	-n	ty	concerning him-her-it	-n	toj-tja-to	concerning him-her-it	-s
4.	ja	concerning us	-s	ty	concerning us	-t	toj-tja-to	concerning us	-n
5.	ja	concerning you (plural)	-t	ty	concerning you (plural)	-s	toj-tja-to	concerning you (plural)	-t
6.	ja	concerning them	-n	ty	concerning them	-n	toj-tja-to	concerning them	-s
7.	nýje	concerning me	-s	výje	concerning me	-t	tíje-to-to-to	concerning me	-n
8.	nýje	concerning you	-t	výje	concerning you	-s	tíje-to-to-to	concerning you	-t

9.	nýje	concerning him-her-it	-n	výje	concerning him-her-it	-n	tíje-to-to-to	concerning him-her-it	-s
10.	nýje	concerning us	-s	výje	concerning us	-t	tíje-to-to-to	concerning us	-n
11.	nýje	concerning you (plural)	-t	výje	concerning you (plural)	-s	tíje-to-to-to	concerning you (plural)	-t
12.	nýje	concerning them	-n	výje	concerning them	-n	tíje-to-to-to	concerning them	-s

The tripartite article brings Pomak close to the so-called ‘Rupski’ dialect continuum, which is generally considered to be dialectal Bulgarian (Stoykov 1968: 128–143; Scatton 2002: 245). However, this is the main trait that connects Pomak with its northern relative ‘Rupski’ Bulgarian; this can be easily verified by looking at a list of ‘Rupski’ traits (Stoykov 1968: 128–143; Scatton 2002: 245). The fact that the Bulgarian dialect is spoken north of Rhodope mountains explains the name ‘Rupski (< Rup)’, which means ‘pertaining to Rhodope; Rhodopian’.

2.6 A *WHERE*-relativiser

Probably under the influence of Modern Greek vernaculars, Pomak has a *WHERE*-relativiser consisting of an indeclinable *WHERE*-part (*de* < OCS *къде* ‘where’) + plus the suffixed *N*-definite article: *déno* (ο που ‘ο οποίος’) - *déna* (η που ‘η οποία’) - *déno* (το που ‘το οποίο’) (Krimpas 2020: 188–189), cf. Modern Greek (now dialectal) *ο που αγαπά* ‘the one who loves, *lit.* *the where loves’, cf. Standard Modern Greek *αυτός που αγαπά(ει)* ‘the one who love, *lit.* *he where loves’.

2.7 Reflection of yat (ǫ/ǣ) as an [ɛɐ] diphthong

This diphthong, which can also be pronounced as [æ], derives from Old Church Slavonic yat (ǫ), which is usually considered as pronounced [æ] (Kyranoudis 1996: 169) but it could well have also the diphthongised pronunciation [ɛɐ], which is why it is often reflected as [ja] in Polish and Bulgarian and as [ije] in Croatian. As a sound, this diphthong occurs only in Slovak after labial consonants (*pät* ‘five’), while its [æ] version is comparable to the Russian allophone of я /ja/ following labial consonants (*пять* ‘five’) and the Bulgarian Rupian development of OCS /a/ after alveo-palatals (Scatton 2002: 245); however, in both Slovak and Russian it derives from Proto-Slavic yer rather than yat:

Pomak	Old Church Slavonic
mǣsto ‘field’	мѣсто ‘place’
bǣl ‘white’	бѣль ‘id.’
hlǣb ‘bread’	хлѣбъ ‘id.’

The existence of this pronunciation of yat typologically connects Pomak with more northern Slavic languages.

2.8 Masculine personal form in the adjectival declension

Like most Slavic languages, Pomak has inherited the Indo-European three-gender nominal system (masculine, feminine, and neutral). However, Proto-Slavic had an animate masculine vs. inanimate masculine distinction as well, which in most modern Slavic languages is visible in the fact that in animate masculine nouns the accusative singular is identical with their genitive singular. Moreover, some West Slavic languages, namely Polish, Kashubian and Slovak have developed certain grammatical distinctions between a personal masculine and a non-personal masculine class of nouns, a distinction visible only in the nominative and accusative plural. Generally speaking, personal masculine nominative plural is marked by sibilantisation and/or palatalisation of the stem consonant and an /i/ (spelled *i*) rather than a -sometimes only historical (as in Slovak, which now pronounces it as /i/) /ĭ/ (spelled *y*) nominative plural ending (although Polish has reverted to /y/ following *c, cz, rz, sz, ź* due to phonotactic reasons). Sometimes the stem of personal masculine nominal words undergoes various consonant mutations before the personal masculine nominative plural ending is added, e.g. *dobrzy Włosi* ‘good Italians’, *dobrzy Polacy* ‘good Poles’, but cf. *dobre stoły* ‘good tables’, *Piątki* ‘Fridays’. Besides, personal masculine nouns can take non-personal endings when used pejoratively, e.g. *te Warszawiaki* ‘those bloody Warsawians’ instead of *te Warszawiacy* ‘those Warsawians’ (Rothstein 2002: 696–697). A similar situation (with slight differences such as the inclusion of some animals in the personal masculine class) exists in Kashubian (Polański 2002: 768–769) and Slovak (Short 2002: 540). Interestingly, Pomak practices this distinction, although only in the adjectival declension (i.e. in adjectives, participles and 3rd person plural pronouns); this makes it very different from other ESS languages, e.g. *mládi afkátje* ‘young lawyers’, *mlády hórehy* ‘young walnut trees’. The existence of a personal masculine and non-personal masculine class typologically connects Pomak with more northern Slavic languages.

2.9 Noun inflection

Most Slavic languages reflect the Old Church Slavonic pattern of seven case forms (nominative, genitive, dative, accusative, locative, instrumental, and eventually vocative) in singular, plural and dual (the latter now surviving only in Slovene). However, the standardised ESS languages, namely Bulgarian and Macedonian, have lost all cases, except for a masculine *casus absolutus* which makes for all original oblique cases. Pomak is again unique among ESS languages in retaining four cases, namely nominative, genitive/dative, accusative and vocative, a system reminding of the Modern Greek one (Krimpas 2020: 183–184); indeed, Modern Greek is considered the source of case syncretism in the Balkans (Krapova & Dimitrova 2015: 191). Pomak inflection is both conservative and innovative, given that the case retention as such is conservative, but the loss and syncretism of some cases is innovative:

Case	Singular	Plural
Nominative	góram	górmove
Genitive/Dative	górmu	górmovem
Accusative	góрма	górmove
Vocative	górmu	górmove

Case	Singular	Plural
Nominative	lámba	lámby

Genitive/Dative	lámboj	lámboj
Accusative	lámbo	lámby
Vocative	lámbo	lámby

Case	Singular	Plural
Nominative	kóte	kóteta
Genitive/Dative	kótetu	kótetom
Accusative	kóte	kóteta
Vocative	kóte	kóteta

The existence of a case system typologically connects Pomak with more northern Slavic languages.

2.10 Residual infinitive

Proto-Slavic and OSC both had an infinitive, which has been retained in all modern Slavic languages with the exception of Bulgarian and Macedonian. However, Pomak is again unique among ESS in retaining a truncated (i.e. without the *-ti* ending) form of infinitive, which is used in set structures such as the prohibitive, e.g. *namój pisavá* ‘do not write (all the time, imperfective aspect)’, *namój pisá* ‘do not write (now, perfective aspect)’, although its functions are very limited in comparison with the original OCS infinitive. Interestingly, a similar truncated infinitive also exists in Romanian (e.g. *a purta* < Lat. *portare*), which suggests that this truncation of the infinitive is a Balkanism connecting Slavic Pomak with Romance Romanian. The existence of an infinitive typologically connects Pomak with more northern Slavic languages.

3. Conclusions

The above discussion clearly shows that Pomak is an idiosyncratic East South Slavic language, which, although a close relative of Bulgarian and Macedonian, does exhibit numerous unique innovative and conservative traits that set it apart from the above two languages. In this paper we examined only ten individualising traits (six innovative and four conservative ones). Half of those traits even bring Pomak closer to North (i.e. West and East) Slavic languages such as Polish, Russian, Kashubian, Slovak or Belausian. But Pomak is idiosyncratic not only in comparison to its closest relatives (Bulgarian and Macedonian), but even in comparison to non-Slavic Balkan languages. All this suggests that Pomak – at least as spoken within what is now Greece – is by no means a ‘Bulgarian’ dialect, but rather as a clearly demarcated non-standardised East South Slavic dialect continuum with its own phonology, lexicon, grammar and syntax. It is an idiosyncratic Slavic language that deserves more study and – why not? – standardisation.

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